

Nikkei як повноцінна крос-медійна система

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Наукова стаття присвячена крос-медійній системі, що побудована навколо японської економічної газети *Nikkei*. Розглянуті явище крос-медіа, передумови його виникнення в Японії, а також його функціонування на прикладі завершеної крос-медійної платформи, побудованої *Nikkei*. Дослідження показує, як щоденна друкована преса Японії еволюціонує від традиційної медіамоделі до крос-медіа. У розвідці представлено особливості найвпливовішої економічної газети *Nikkei*, її історія, тематичні особливості та різні канали, через які аудиторія споживає інформацію в рамках крос-медійної системи. Окрім цього, автор аналізує наклад різних видань газети, прослідковуючи його зміни з 2012 по 2019 р. Досліджується, як у газеті вибудовується крос-медійна платформа навколо друкованих медіа, онлайн-видань, телебачення, радіо, інформаційних мереж; участь в освітніх проектах та виставках, а також впровадження елементів доповненої реальності. Наукова робота зіставляє категорії крос-медіа за Гері Хейзом з крос-медійними елементами *Nikkei*, що ілюструють кожну з категорій. Автор статті також прослідковує, яким чином *Nikkei* виходить на світовий ринок, аналізує процеси глобалізації та дигіталізації японської медіамоделі. Визначено зв'язок між розвитком онлайн-елементів крос-медіа та повільним зниженням накладів друкованих видань. Результати роботи можуть бути використані для подальших досліджень японської теорії медіа у вітчизняному та іноземному наукових дискурсах.

Ключові слова: *Nikkei*; крос-медіа; категорії крос-медіа; економічна газета; японська медіамоделі; глобалізація; дигіталізація.

1. Introduction

Problem statement. Nowadays Japanese media model represents one of the most developed cross media systems in the world. People have access to the information they need through different media channels and devices. Day after day cross media systems are becoming more and more complicated. In contemporary media sphere, cross media platform not only informs the audience, it connects, educates, guides the people and interacts with them. Cross media are also related to globalization and digitalization of Japanese media. *Nikkei* is a complete cross media system, which gives a good depiction of how cross media in Japan works.

Latest research works and publications analysis. In the process of research, the works written by the following scholars were analyzed: Gary Hayes (cross-media theory), Alli Mcharazo and Sjoerd Koopman (information society studies), Fukushima Yoshinao, Stanislav Lukin, Kawata Shinya and Fujiwara Yoshi, Hayashi Kaori, Anthony Rausch (theory and history of the Japanese media).

Purpose of the paper. The scientific paper aims to show how cross media in Japan works, taking *Nikkei* Shimbun as an example. The research illustrates how cross media categories developed by Gary Hayes are represented in the *Nikkei* cross media system.

Research object – *Nikkei* cross-media system.

Research methods. To scrutinize the structure of the Japanese daily newspaper market and analyze various *Nikkei* editions and cross-media elements we used the systematic analysis. Cross-media itself is a complicated system, therefore systematic analysis is considered to be a useful and sufficient method in our research. It helps us to trace, distinguish and analyze all relations between various media elements inside a cross-media platform, such as different printed editions of *Nikkei*, its broadcast and online media. We used descriptive method to categorize *Nikkei* topics and history, to give detailed explanation of how *Nikkei* media channels such as press (newspapers, magazines), television, radio, web sites, online media, data networks, different interactions with audience etc. work within the cross-media platform. In terms of cross-media, each part of the system relates to the other in many ways, so this method provides us with the best tools to decompose the object of our research and analyze its elements precisely. Descriptive method is useful in our work since it gives the researcher an opportunity to describe the object of the paper, give all necessary information that helps to understand the background of the research and all the processes, terms and statistics that deal with the topic. Eventually, we used structural analysis to create a model which depicts interactions between *Nikkei* media channels and cross-media categories by Gary Hayes. It is one of the most important methods in our research, which puts

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together each part of the work, and lets us scrutinize the different elements in juxtaposition. We build a structural model of *Nikkei* cross media system, we compare, analyze, match specific facts and data with theoretical categories to understand what cross-media is as a phenomenon, how it is represented in Japan, why Japan is the leading country in terms of development of cross media systems, and how a particular complete cross-media platform in Japan works with *Nikkei* as an example.

2. Results

At the beginning of mass media era people were limited to newspapers, which often were the organs of certain organizations or governments. Subsequently steady technological progress led to invention of new means of mass media. XIX century gave us the radio, television and the Internet, and 1980s proclaimed the establishment of the information society, “a society in which the creation, distribution, and manipulation of information has become the most significant economic and cultural activity” [1, p. 52]. Post-war Japan chose very effective strategies to restore country’s economics. Up to 1980s Japan became one of the leaders at the technological and media markets. High standard of living led to effective development of market services and information society. Japanese people got the freedom to create and consume: art, literature, media and technologies. Scholar Stanislav Lukin states that “a democratic regime in Japan formed in economics decline period, and a switch-over to a democratic rule was implanted from outside by the forces of the Alliance”. According to Lukin, media institutions formation in Japan use two types of rules which determine the structured order of the media sphere: inherited socially generated rules, and the rules borrowed by the American government at the end of World War II [2]. These rules affected the contemporary look of Japanese media model.

Contemporary model of Japanese daily newspapers is represented by so-called “newspaper pyramid”, which includes five of the most influential daily newspapers with the highest circulations: *Yomiuri Shimbun* (8.5 million copies in the morning and 2.4 in the evening), *Asahi Shimbun* (5.9 million in the morning and 1.8 in the evening), *Mainichi Shimbun* (2.4 million in the morning and 680 000 thousand in the evening), *Nikkei* (2.3 million in the morning and 1.1 in the evening) and *Sankei Shimbun* (1.3 million in the morning and 350 000 thousand in the evening) [3; 4; 5, p. 3]. Scholar Anthony Rausch says that “Students read the ‘*Yomiuri*’; the employed the ‘*Nikkei*’; and the retired read the ‘*Asahi*’” [6, p. 96]. Moreover, there is at least one local newspaper in 47 Japanese prefectures. Scholar Hayashi Kaori stresses that “Japan is a newspaper country—the Japanese people are devoted readers of newspapers and the number of newspaper readers is high compared to the most part of other countries,” and “ninety-five percent of newspapers are delivered to regular subscribers’ homes” [5, p. 3]. In October 2018, the total circulation of newspapers in Japan was almost 39.9 million, which amounts to 0.7 copies per household [7]. But online versions of newspapers, available on any devices, become more and more popular. Thus, the circulations of printed media have slightly fallen throughout the last decade, and the number of online subscribers has increased. Development of information society allowed mass media to manage different

communication channels, providing their audiences with information in many ways. This phenomenon was called cross-media. It suggests “distribution of media content via different means of mass media and distribution channels” [8, p. 92]. Traditional printed media now transform into cross-media production, which spreads content via different means of media, such as newspapers, magazines, TV, radio, Internet, data networks and news agencies, educational and research programs, exhibitions and establishment of media for global audience overseas.

One of the most influential modern cross media platforms in Japan is represented by *Nikkei*. *Nikkei Shimbun* is Japanese daily newspaper devoted to economics. It represents the complex cross media platform which is present in different forms of media at domestic and global markets. *Nikkei Shimbun* is a part of *Nikkei Media Group*, which also owns *TV Tokyo* and *Nikkei CNBC channels*, “*Nikkei Broadcasting*” radio network, *Nikkei BP* magazine publishing house, which publishes several specialized magazines, such as “*Nikkei Architecture*,” “*Nikkei Women Online*,” “*Nikkei Business Online*,” “*Nikkei Trends*,” “*Nikkei Medicine*,” “*Nikkei Technologies Online*,” etc. There are 29 magazines with more than 2 million readers, and 10 websites, whose total number of online monthly views reached 110 million per month (almost as big as population in Japan), and there were 20 million unique users in 2020 [9, p. 2]. The core of *Nikkei Media Group* is *Nikkei Shimbun*. The history of the newspaper shows that in the last decade its main directions were globalization and digitalization. *Nikkei* as a newspaper publisher was established in 1876, and since then it has become the most trusted economic newspaper in Japan. In 2010 the Online edition was launched, in 2011 – *Nikkei Asian Review*, an English-language weekly magazine. The newspaper started a Chinese Edition, a Chinese-language website in 2012 and online edition of the *Nikkei Asian Review* in 2013 [10, p. 2]. One of the most important dates in modern history of the newspaper is 2015, when *Nikkei Group* bought *the Financial Times*, the most famous American financial newspaper. The deal cost 1.3 billion dollars [11]. Nowadays *Nikkei* has the largest circulation as an economic daily newspaper in the world [10, p. 3]. Its nearest rivals are *The Wall Street Journal* (USA, 2.2 million copies, 2018), *The Economic Times* (India, 368 000 thousand, 2018), *Financial Times* (168 958 thousand, 2018) and *Il Sole 24 Ore* (Italy, 117 688 thousand, 2018) [3; 12; 13]. There are many editions of *Nikkei* in Japan and overseas. The main edition has 2 printed versions: the morning and the afternoon one. In addition to them there is also a website with certain publications posted for free and the paid online version of *Nikkei Shimbun*. Moreover, *Nikkei* has regional editions in Japan: in Tokyo, Nagoya, Osaka, Kyushu and Hokkaido [10, p. 4]. The bigger part of the circulation printed with 24 full-colour pages, the rest comes with color top and culture pages, other are black and white. In Hokkaido and some areas in Tokyo and Osaka regions *Nikkei* is sold with colour top and culture pages only [10, p. 4]. *Nikkei* is also present at the global media market. Official web site states that “*Nikkei* provides a global perspective and in-depth analyses to Japanese readers, transmitting information that is essential for businesspeople and investors” [10, p. 5]. The newspaper has 37 news bureaus around the world, which gather news mainly in Europe, Asia and

Table 1. Nikkei Editions with Circulations
Data retrieved from [4; 9, p. 2; 10, p. 3–4]

Nikkei Edition	Circulation		Year
Morning	2.9 / 2.7 / 2.3 million		2012 / 2017 / 2019
Afternoon	1.5 / 1.3 / 1.1 million		2012 / 2017 / 2019
Online	546 877 / 650 000 paid subscribers		2017 / 2019
Nikkei BP Magazines (29 editions, 10 sites)	2 million / 110 million views per month/ 20 million unique users		2020
Tokyo Morning	1.6 million	~1.4 million with 24 colour pages	2017
Tokyo Afternoon	795 749		2017
Nagoya Morning	190 569	~190 000 with 24 colour pages	2017
Nagoya Afternoon	105 679		2017
Osaka Morning	715 164	~590 000 with 24 colour pages	2017
Osaka Afternoon	381 732		2017
Kyushu Morning	163 794	~ 130 000 with 24 colour pages	2017
Kyushu Afternoon	48 318		2017
Hokkaido Morning	47 319		2017
Hokkaido Afternoon	0		2017
American	8400		2017
European	6000		2017
Asian	19 900		2017

the United States. They are operated by more than 240 journalists. *Nikkei* publishes American, European and Asian editions with total circulation up to 34 400 copies. According to official *Nikkei* website and Japan Audit Bureau of Circulations, total domestic circulation reaches 3.4 million copies [10, p. 3–4].

Nikkei Online is the cross media itself. After establishing in 2010 it developed in complex system, which gives the audience different services in addition to information. Readers of *Nikkei Online* now choose not only what to read, but how to read and when. *Nikkei* calls their web newspaper “Japan’s first full-fledged subscription news site”, implying that there is no better alternative, and they implemented everything that was possible in cross media. The newspaper says that “The web edition delivers the latest news, commentaries, features and columns around the clock, with sections thematically categorized by optional experience.” *Nikkei Online* features access to the entire print versions of the morning and afternoon issues of the newspaper. Paid users can read them specifically reformatted for convenient reading on smartphones, tablets and other devices. There is also a Paper Viewer mode, where full pages of the newspaper are shown. Online reading also includes all supplements such as Chiki Keizai (local economy). “My *Nikkei*” is a personalized function set offered to subscribers, which includes automatic article collection based on keywords, and personal archive where readers can store any article they like. *Nikkei ID* is subscription service which allows people to have 2 different types of subscription to *Nikkei*. If you are the reader of the print version of *Nikkei*, you pay 1000 yen per month to get full access to *Nikkei Online*. Online-only subscription costs 4000 yen. In such a way *Nikkei* supports its printed version. In addition, all users can read certain articles online for free, and registered users can get access to up to 20 paid articles for free each month [10, p. 6–7].

Nikkei publishes approximately 125 000 articles every year, and there are three main topics: economics, politics, and sports. There are roughly 10 000 articles each month with on average 45 000 unique words [14, p. 423–425]. *Nikkei Online* has the following headings:

1. **News Flash.** The latest news updated 24\7 and browsable by different criteria.

2. **Business Leader.** The rubric targeted on executives and managerial-level employees. *Nikkei* states that they constitute 40% of its readers.

3. **Technology.** Contains IT market and technologies business information. According to the newspaper, 30% of its readers are general managers or higher, and 60% are managers or higher.

4. **Life.** Miscellaneous things about daily life and household finance for students, businesspeople and homemakers.

5. **Sports.** Covering main worldwide sports events with online scoreboard.

6. **Money.** This heading features important information for investors such as the latest financial data, investment and management strategies, financial columns etc. It also represents the digest from *Nikkei Money Magazine*.

7. **Market.** Detailed data on currency, stock trends and commodities from QUICK Corp. – financial market information vendor with headquarters in Tokyo, owned by *Nikkei* [10, p. 3].

This company is a well-known developer of Japanese news database service in real time. The other two alternatives are *Nikkei Telecom* and *Jiji News Wire* [15]. Additionally, QUICK calculates the widely recognized in financial circles stock market index *Nikkei 225* [16]. *Nikkei* also owns one more financial database, the mentioned above *Nikkei Telecom*. About 70% of top-class Japanese companies are the subscribers of this database. *Nikkei Telecom’s* “articles are cross-searchable from over 500 different sources and the most up-to-date business news is taken from the *Nikkei* and other leading Japanese newspapers, magazines and journals.” It also contains companies’ and businesspeople’s profiles [17]. *Nikkei* also runs *Nikkei Biz* business academy, with lectures given by professors of Waseda University and others (1000+ seminars a year). *Nikkei Biz* takes part in different business forums such as MBA Expo,

annual event for leading business, accounting schools in and outside Japan, holds over 40 trade shows [9, p. 2; 10, p. 14].

Nikkei Radio Broadcasting Corporation owns *Nikkei Radio*, which was established in 1954 and has two channels, Radio 1 and 2. It is nationwide free-to-air commercial radio, which covers the following topics: horse racing, finance, culture and health [18]. *Nikkei* also owns TV Tokyo Corporation, well-known television station with 128 667-million-yen revenue. It has been operating since 1964. TV Tokyo features economic, news, sports, music, travel, entertainment, documentary programs, anime, TV drama and movies [19]. On top of that, *Nikkei* runs Nikkei CNBC financial TV channel, which covers a variety of business topics. Its audience is more than 400 million households around the world with offices in Europe, North America, Asia and Japan [20].

To sum up, let us see the structure of *Nikkei* cross media system as a whole, and look which categories of cross media developed by Hayes (read more about cross media categories here [21]) it uses in the table 2.

number of *Nikkei Online* paid subscribers increased from 546 thousand in 2017 to 650 thousand in 2019. It proves that development of digital media affects the printed media market, making the audience prefer more convenient online media, which they can read basically everywhere, thanks to their availability for mobile devices and high level of Internet penetration in Japan. *Nikkei* knows it and tries to prevent immense circulation downfall, setting the price for online-only subscription 4 times higher than printed newspaper + online subscription (4000 yen versus 1000). Thus, extension of cross media system and development of its online and mobile media elements results in decline of the printed edition's circulation.

4. Conclusions

Nikkei Media Group created full-blown cross media platform, which combines printed media (newspapers, magazines), broadcasting (TV and radio networks), online media (websites, online newspapers and magazines, mobile

Table 2. Nikkei Cross Media Categories

Cross-media	Pushed	Extras	Bridges	Experiences
Nikkei Printed Media (Newspaper, Nikkei BP magazines)	Pushes articles from printed edition to Nikkei Online	Newspaper supplements; specialized magazines complement newspaper rubrics	Make readers of the newspaper visit the website	Nikkei AR App – application for mobile devices, which can be downloaded for free for iOS and Android. AR means augmented reality, and it allows users to scan the markers in printed edition of Nikkei Shimbun (on ads or articles) to display the augmented reality elements, such as video, music, news, additional data. It also provides interactivity allowing readers to share the information with friends via social networks and messengers, and even apply for Nikkei campaigns or events [22].
Nikkei Online	20 paid articles pushed to free website each month for registered users	Extra articles for paid subscribers, additional financial data	Advertises other Nikkei media (newspaper, magazines, TV)	
Nikkei Broadcasting Corporation (TV Tokyo, Nikkei CNBC, Nikkei Radio)	Develops the topics from other Nikkei media in TV programs and reportages	Provides unique information (e. g. travel shows, anime on TV, horse racing reports on radio)	Links other audiences to Nikkei via TV programs (e. g. anime fans via anime shows on TV Tokyo)	
Nikkei business data network (QUICK Corp., Nikkei Telecom)	Gives data to other Nikkei media (Nikkei Index, stock markets etc.)	Provides detailed personalized information to subscribers	Connects its users with other Nikkei media	
Globalization ↓ ↓ ↓				
Financial Times	Pushes the information to the global market, adds foreign audiences, increases Nikkei brand recognition around the world, transfers the information to other languages. Provides mobile applications and web sites in different languages.			
Nikkei Asian Review				
Nikkei Chinese				
Nikkei Biz Academy	Pushes the media into the scientific context, teaches the students, holds international events for business schools in and outside Japan, provides globalization of Japanese financial media discourse.			

3. Discussion

Japanese media model faces the process of media convergence, globalization and digitalization. Analysis of the circulation data presented above shows that since 2012 circulation of printed issues of the newspaper has been steadily decreasing. In 2012 total sales of the morning and afternoon *Nikkei Shimbun* were 4.4 million copies, in 2017 – 4 million, in 2019 it fell to 3.4 copies [4; 10, p. 3–4]. Printed edition lost 1 million of circulation in the last decade. From the other hand, the

applications), financial data networks, global media editions in different languages and business academy. They effectively use all categories of cross media, distinguished by Gary Hayes, who states that cross media 4.0 (experiences) (read more [21]) combines all previous levels and distributes content “across many platforms in non-linear way,” and “across many devices.” This is exact description of how Nikkei cross media system works. And eventually it results in Nikkei Augmented Reality application, which combines all media elements together (printed text, online text, video, music, augmented reality and

interactivity), giving all users an experience to live their own story in the journey across the continents of Nikkei Media world.

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Pashchenko B. Nikkei as a complete cross-media system

The scientific paper is devoted to the cross-media system which is built around Japanese economic newspaper *Nikkei*. The work considers the phenomenon of cross-media, the preconditions of its establishment in Japan, and its functioning with complete *Nikkei* cross-media platform as an example. Research shows how traditional Japanese daily press evolves into cross-media. The academic work considers the peculiarities of the most influential economic newspaper *Nikkei*, its history, topics and different channels through which the audience consumes information within the cross-media system. In addition, the author analyzes the circulation of various editions of the newspaper, tracing its changes from 2012 to 2019. The article analyzes how the newspaper builds a cross-media platform around print media, online publications, television, radio, information networks, participation in educational projects and exhibitions, and the introduction of augmented reality elements. The research compares cross-media categories by Gary Hayes with *Nikkei* cross-media elements, illustrating each category. The author also considers how *Nikkei* enters the global market, analyzes the processes of globalization and digitization of Japanese media model. The author defines the relationship between the development of online cross-media elements and the steady decline of the print circulations. The results of the work can be used for the further studies of Japanese media theory in domestic and foreign scientific discourses.

Keywords: *Nikkei; cross-media; categories of cross-media; economic newspaper; Japanese media model; globalization; digitalization.*

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